

Fundamentals of using collaborative technologies in teaching the visual arts

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Annotation: The article is split into three units: brand fundamentals, process basics and case studies. It provides in-depth guidance for both designers and entire branding groups, walking you through a universal five-stage process for brand development and implementation. Bringing together around many brands, The author examines the distillation of modernism in graphic design and how these attitudes and imperatives gave birth to corporate identity. These inspirational designs are organized into three chapters – geometric, effect and typographic – and provide a comprehensive index to inform your own work. Anyone working in logo design will get a lot out of this book.

Keywords: information, culture, paints, computer, designer, picture, filmstrips, video, advertising posters

Therefore, the creation of the theoretical and practical foundations of the use of pedagogical technologies in visual art classes on the basis of the effective use of the opportunities of modern educational technologies determines the relevance of the research. Level of study of the problem.

According to the documents of the Ministries of Public Education and Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the goals of modern education are not to train a narrow range of specialists for a specific field of activity, but to develop the personality of each person, pedagogy in fine arts classes. the use of technologies is its effective implementation. The use of interactive teaching methods in painting classes in fine arts is one of the current issues. The need to apply pedagogical technologies to visual art classes from interactive methods such as brainstorming, cluster, conversation, debate, discussion, puzzle, role-playing games arises based on the study and analysis of the content of pedagogical technology and the essence of traditional education.

It is well known to us that the content of traditional education is mainly built on the basis of the authoritarian position of the pedagogue in this process, the slow activity of visual art students, and the main part of the time allocated for visual art is spent on important theoretical knowledge by pedagogues. was used to describe information, it was expressed that the need to ensure the activity of students of visual arts was not felt. Until now, there has not been any more systematic scientific work or methodical-didactic manual published on the issue of pedagogical technology in teaching the science of painting in school fine art. In order to think about this issue, it would be better to start the issue a little higher and analyze the use of technology, pedagogical technology, and then the use of new pedagogical technology in the teaching of visual arts - in our opinion.

For this, first of all, it is necessary to study the lessons of visual art at school. It is known that school visual arts lessons are carried out in the form of five types of training or technology. 1. Making a picture according to the object. 2. Work on the thematic composition. 3. Decorative practical - decorative art. 4. Sculpture works. 5. Classes are conducted on the basis of art studies Although the teaching technology of this lesson has the same content, the teaching technology in them is definitely different from each other.

The development of color vision in students will be more effective if certain conditions are met: - has developed a methodological system for developing the color vision of students; - if a set of tasks and exercises has been developed aimed at developing the color vision of students in

a children's art school; -if the information is provided taking into account new developments in the field of color science; if non-traditional technologies are used to create a favorable atmosphere in painting classes; - if the work of each student is checked according to developed assessment criteria, taking into account the psychological and age characteristics of each child. As a child grows up, this ability very often fades away and disappears without a trace. If a student is not taught the basics of color science in visual literacy, then later he begins to understand that his drawing is completely implausible. Disappointment in one's abilities sets in, and interest in drawing disappears. When depicting a landscape, scenes of human life, the drawing must be convincing and similar to the original. In the visual arts, an important means of expression is color, which students are introduced to in painting lessons, according to the basics of color science, using color to convey an image in their image. Painting classes allow students to develop skills in working with color. , the ability to use colors as a means of expressiveness in fine art. The most significant achievement of the educational process for students is the level of development of their color vision. Conclusion In an atmosphere of high humanitarian culture and only on the basis of broad humanization of school education, mastery of the wealth of world artistic culture, it is possible to educate a person who strives for self-realization and has a sense of social responsibility, knows how to use and appreciate the spiritual and material wealth of society and contributes to the restoration and enrichment of its spirituality.

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